

Development of a Professional Governance Evaluation Toolkit

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Background

- Shared Governance (SG) is a structure with processes that support participative leadership. SG cultivates the ownership of both professional practice and the work environment establishing Professional Governance (PG).

Significance

- Strategies for evaluating PG are inconsistent in the literature.
- Evaluation of PG identifies opportunities for improvement
- Outcomes identified from PG are justification for the costs:
 - Paid time for council meetings and activities
 - Paid time for council leadership training & QI education

Project Aims

Evaluate the correlation between perceptions of PG and:

- Leadership position (frontline v. administrative)
- Council membership status (member v. non-member)
- Years of experience in PG
- Number of PG facilitation strategies implemented in a department
- RN engagement scores
- Culture of safety scores
- Patient experience score
- RN turnover rates

Determine PG outcomes:

- PG outcomes and cost savings
- Compare year over year outcomes

Supporting Framework

Results

Perceptions of PG significantly correlated with membership on a PG council, RN engagement scores, culture of safety, and RN turnover. Patient experience scores and facilitation methods did not correlate with PG in this assessment.

Health Care Clinician Characteristic Associations	p-value
Frontline v. Administrative Status	0.24
Council Membership Status	0.004
Years of Experience in PG	0.79

Correlational Analysis	p-value
Facilitation Checklist	0.13
RN Engagement Benchmark Gap	<.001
Culture of Safety Benchmark Gap	<.001
Patient Experience Benchmark Gap	0.24
Rate of Turnover	0.01

PG Toolkit Scorecard

Dept	RN Perceptions of Governance Performance	RN Engagement Benchmark Gap	RN Safety Culture Benchmark Gap	RN Turnover Benchmark Gap	Patient Experience Benchmark Gap	Total Fiscal Year Outcomes Achieved	Total \$oft Savings
Overall	5.56	0.2	0.21	6.20%	10.3	TBD	TBD
PICU	6.18	-0.01	0.17	1.99%	8		
CVICU	5.53	-0.2	-0.11	14.60%	2.4		
NICU	4.99	0.21	0.12	2.28%	-6.5		
ED	n too low	0.32	0.2	-3.49%	0.8		
Medical	5.89	0.31	0.11	-1.22%	6.3		
Surgical	5.72	0.14	0.16	-0.66%	13.4		
Recovery Center	n too low	0.03	-0.15	7.99%	n/a		
Main OR	n too low	-0.29	-0.34	4.74%	-1.8		
Oncology	n too low	0.46	0.21	15.45%	-2.5		
Mental Health	n too low	0.14	0.12	-5.38%	1.8		
Multispecialty	n too low	0.53	0.5	-1.86%	0.4		
Neuroscience Unit	n too low	-0.09	0.12	-5.02%	n/a		
Float Pool	n too low	0.44	0.26	-9.55%	n/a		
Transport	n too low	0.12	0.09	4.01%	n/a		

Discussion

- PG engages nurses in activities that provide them decisional authority over their practice.
- Organizational support for authority and autonomy increases engagement enhancing collegiality, reducing turnover, and increases ownership of the quality of care provided.

Limitations

- Inconsistent PG models across healthcare limit generalizability.
- COVID-19 Pandemic resulted in a prolonged low census causing reduced staff hours and PG meetings were cancelled at the time of the survey.
- This may have caused reduced PG perceptions, lowered engagement scores, and increased turnover.
- Response rates to the survey were low due to the length of the survey (84 items) therefore limiting the ability to analyze individual department performance.

Implications for Practice

- A comprehensive evaluation of PG is important to determine if the investments have successfully produced the intended empirical outcomes.
- Reassessment at regular intervals is recommended.

Additional Information

Toolkit Components

References

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